

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ІНСТРУМЕНТАРІЙ АНАЛІЗУ СТАНУ СОЦІАЛЬНОЇ ВІДПОВІДАЛЬНОСТІ ПІДПРИЄМСТВА ДЛЯ ПОТРЕБ УПРАВЛІННЯ РОЗВИТКОМ

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ANALYSIS TOOLS TO ASSESS THE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY OF THE ENTERPRISE FOR DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT NEEDS

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АНОТАЦІЯ

У роботі виокремлено основні етапи методики аналізування та здійснено аналіз рівня соціальної відповідальності вітчизняних підприємств з метою ідентифікування факторів успіху, що можуть бути враховані менеджментом підприємства у процесі вибору напрямків здійснення заходів соціальної спрямованості. Виявлено низький рівень поінформованості регіональних органів управління про соціально відповідальний бізнес. Наведено результати моніторингу ставлення управлінських структур до необхідності впровадження системи корпоративної соціальної відповідальності підприємств України на основі матриці компанії Sustain Ability. У процесі дослідження ідентифіковано й систематизовано показники макросередовища за зовнішніми векторами та здійснено аналіз стану соціальної відповідальності вітчизняних підприємств на рівні національної економіки.

ABSTRACT

The main stages of the methodology of analysis are allocated in the work and the analysis of the level of social responsibility of domestic enterprises is carried out in order to identify the factors of success that can be taken into account by the management of the enterprise in the process of choosing the directions of implementation of measures of social orientation. There is a lack of awareness among regional management bodies about socially responsible business. The results of monitoring the attitude of management structures to the need to introduce a system of corporate social responsibility of enterprises of Ukraine on the basis of the matrix of Sustain Ability are presented. During the studying process, external vectors identified and systematized indicators of the macro environment, and an analysis of the state of social responsibility of domestic enterprises at the national economy was conducted.

Ключові слова: соціально відповідальне підприємство, управління, нефінансова звітність, аналіз.

Keywords: socially responsible enterprise, management, non-financial reporting, analysis.

Introduction. The transformation of the national economy requires a new management toolkit based on knowledge and culture. The foundation for development should be the combination of these two basic phenomena. The value system is based on the experience gained, supported by proven facts, and is geared towards human potential, which is not focused on technical potential, but on human potential. This will lead to more effective management and awareness of the integrity of the organization, which will in turn lead to the achievement of the goal.

Awareness of responsibility is inherent in business, which is carried out in a social environment, and therefore undertakes the obligation to create decent conditions for its workers, to preserve the sustainable environment of its existence (a certain territory, community interests), and the environment (waste disposal,

prevention of damage to ecosystems). Responsibility to society is dictated by its needs when there is a need to unite efforts to solve certain problems, which requires the creation of special institutions on which society entrusts the functions of protecting a person and creating a safe environment in environmental, legal, humanitarian and other aspects.

The need for corporate social responsibility is still not recognized in Ukraine. This can be seen both in the passivity of the enterprises themselves and in the lack of structured information at the state level. Every tenth enterprise considers social responsibility a function of the state.

The analysis of existing methods should be the first step in developing the methodology and analyzing the state of social responsibility at the enterprise level. Identifying gaps and removing shortcomings in their

own methodology should be the next step.

Literature review. To this day, the essence of the concept of "social responsibility" is the object of theoretical and practical discussions. The scientific community recognized that the beginning of modern literature on social responsibility was laid in 1953, when the first fundamental work, 'Social Responsibility of a Businessman', was published by a professor of economics at the University of Illinois (USA) Howard R. Bowen [14].

Some scholars recognize only one direction that is worth paying attention to when describing the essence of 'social responsibility'. For example, M. Friedman [16] believes that the only responsibility of business – is the growth of shareholder profits, since business helps society by already producing goods, providing it with necessary services and creating jobs. According to the theory of A. Carroll [19, p. 500], G. Bowen [13, p. 7], the support of social responsibility lies in compliance with the economic, legal, ethical and discretionary expectations of society in a given period of time, but such a statement, in our opinion, is rather an imposition, and not its own conviction of expediency. Awareness of social responsibility, not only as an obligation to society in terms of preserving the environment, the health of employees, and relationships with counterparties, based on corporate rules and regulations, is set forth in the works of Asher Meir [5], Sh. M. Valitov, V. A. Malgin [6, p. 171], O. A. Grishnova [3, p. 54], I. P. Buleev, N. Yu. Bryukhovetskaya, A. V. Chernykh [15, p. 36].

It should be noted that the formation of methods of analysis and evaluation of social responsibility on the basis of corporate culture was formed and improved by such scientists as: Bayura D., Berezina O., Buyan O., Vorobey V., Vorona O., Mazuryk O., Chernykh O.

The main problem in assessing corporate social responsibility is the scientifically based selection of the indicator system, and the primary basis for its solution is the proper choice of areas (objects) of social responsibility.

In general, in the literature and in practice, the theoretical and applied foundations of social responsibility management have not been properly substantiated, the identification of directions for implementing social responsibility measures and indicators for assessing their level and effectiveness of implementation is not systematic enough, the analysis methodology does not provide the proper level of formalization of the social responsibility management process.

The purpose of the study is to develop methodological provisions for analyzing the state of social responsibility of domestic enterprises in external areas of social measures.

The main results of the study. The defining object of the concept of science "social responsibility" is the social relationship between business and nature regarding environmental pollution exclusively with its central component – man [10, p. 17]. The task of this science is to quantify the influence of a business entity

and describe ways to minimize it. But in our opinion, such a theory limits the assessment of the level and sufficiency of social responsibility within the enterprise itself, that is, to its own employees, which is probably the concept of corporate social responsibility.

According to the definition of the World Bank, under the corporate social responsibility (CSR), or equivalent term social responsibility of business (SVB), refers to a set of policies and actions related to key stakeholders and values carried out within the framework of current legislation, as well as taking into account the interests of communities and the environment and the focus of business on sustainable development.

The main reasons that motivate various enterprises to pay special attention to issues of social responsibility are: globalization and the resulting increase in competition; increase the size and influence of companies; strengthening mechanisms of state regulation; "war for talents" – a competition for talented personnel; increased civic engagement; increasing the role of intangible assets (brands) [7].

Usually, to solve the issues of developing their own methods, they start with analyzing information from publicly available sources. The purpose of such a study in our case is the availability of the possibility of analyzing the state of management of social responsibility according to the external vectors of the corporate culture system.

To perform this task, it is necessary to systematize the information in the following sequence: the analysis of the state of management of social responsibility on the basis of monitoring macroeconomic indicators in the context of external vectors; determining the level of awareness of regional management bodies about socially responsible business; monitoring the attitude of management structures to the need to introduce a system of corporate social responsibility of Ukrainian enterprises based on the Sustain Ability company matrix; identification of priority success factors as a result of corporate social management responsibility by external vectors.

To perform the first task, we identified macroeconomic indicators that, in our opinion, characterize the state of management of social responsibility by individual vectors of the corporate culture system (Table 1).

Over the past 10 years, our enterprises have undergone significant modernization, reconstruction, refurbishment. This has a positive impact on the increase in output and sales, which in turn contributes to growth of local tax revenues. Throughout 2015-2019 we see a constant, though not significant, increase in capital investment. Only in 2015 capital investments decreased by 1.8 % compared to the previous year. In subsequent periods, an increase of 18.0 %, 22.1 %, 16.4 %, 15.5 %, respectively, was noted. This indicates that some business entities regularly reinvest in improving their own enterprises, which ultimately will have a positive effect.

Table 1

Indicators structure of the macro environment in the process of analyzing the state of social responsibility management by external vectors

№ п/п	External vectors of social responsibility	Macro environment indicators
1.	Responsibility to the community	The number of unemployed aged 15 -70 years (according to the International Labour Organization methodology), thousand, for reasons of unemployment,%. Average monthly nominal wage *, UAH, average monthly wage real%, the number of full-time employees employed in jobs with harmful working conditions, the number of full-time employees entitled to at least one of the types of benefits and compensation, capital investment%, working conditions of workers by type of economic activity, the number of victims of accidents (acute occupational diseases (poisoning/accidents) and fatal accidents, the number of full-time employees entitled to at least one of the types of benefits and compensation, the number of employees covered by collective agreements, the average monthly salary of full-time employees by types of economic activity in Ukraine as a whole in 2015-2019.
2.	Responsibility for the preservation of the environment and resources	The use of fresh water for the production of million m^3 , discharged into surface water bodies of contaminated return waters without treatment million m^3 , the capacity of treatment facilities million m^3 , emissions of pollutants and carbon dioxide into the atmosphere by stationary sources of pollution thousand tons, generated waste from economic activity of I-IV hazard classes thousand tons, capital investments in environmental protection by types of economic activity.
3.	Responsibility to state fiscal authorities and the state	Financial result before taxation.
4.	Responsibility to customers and customers	Index of industrial producer prices,%, costs of industrial enterprises innovations at the expense of own funds mln. UAH., number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (products and/or technological processes), units.
5.	Responsibility to contractors and partners	Share of the number of businesses that had their own website percent of the total number of businesses.

Source: identified and systematized by authors based on source [12]

As for the vector – responsibility for the preservation of the environment and resources, we consider it expedient to carry out an analysis on such indicators that indicate the volume of use of natural resources and emissions into the environment. Use of fresh water for production during 2015-2019 is on average 4463.8 million m^3 , that is, almost unchanged during the study period. During the studied period, the increase in the volume of reuse of water after purification or cooling differs by 0.7-1.4%. Discharge of surface water bodies of contaminated return water without treatment is reduced by an average of 11.25 million m^3 . The largest decrease occurred in 2016. – for 20 million m^3 and 2018 – for 17 million m^3 , respectively. Such results indicate that enterprises are not interested in investing in the reequipment of the water supply system in order to optimize its use.

Emissions of pollutants and carbon dioxide into the atmosphere by stationary sources of pollution are shown in Fig. 1.

As you can see, emissions are quite high. Compared to 2015 in 2019, there was a decrease of only 13.9%, this is a very low rate of change over 5 years.

If we analyze the volume of emissions of pollutants and carbon dioxide into the atmosphere by stationary sources of pollution by types of economic activity in 2019, it can be concluded that the largest share in the total amount of emissions is formed as a result of the extractive industry and the development of quarries – 17%, enterprises processing industry – 36.2%, pollutants of which metallurgical production - 30.1%, supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning – 39.1%, transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities – 2.2%.

Fig. 1 Emissions of pollutants and carbon dioxide into the atmosphere by stationary sources of pollution thousand tons

Source: built by authors based on source [12]

All other economic activities in the total emissions are 5.5%, which is an average of 0.7% for each individual species.

It should be noted that the volume of generated waste from economic activity of hazard classes I-IV has increased significantly. During the period 2015-2019 there was an increase of 29, 7%. More than half of these wastes during these years were removed to specially designated places or objects 152295,0 thousand tons and 238997,2 thousand tons, respectively. When the volume of accumulation of waste during operation in places of waste disposal according to I, II and III hazard classes during the last 5 years is almost unchanged, the volume of waste of IV hazard class constantly increases during the 2019 year critically, namely by 15.8% compared to 2018.

The largest share in the formation of waste arises from the activities of the mining industry and the development of quarries. In 2018 it was 85, 6%, in 2019 it grew and is 88.5% of the total.

Despite the significant volumes of waste by type of economic activity, capital investments for the protection of the natural environment by mining enterprises are only 2136.2 million UAH, which is only 13.14% of the total in Ukraine. For the processing industry, this figure is twice as high – the volume of capital investments in environmental protection is 4184.5

million UAH. It should be noted that the main part of the cost of environmental protection is the current cost of repairs.

The only macro-indicator that can be informative for the external vector of management of social responsibility – responsibility to state fiscal authorities and the state from publicly available sources is the financial result before taxation,%. During 2018-2019 it grows steadily by slightly more than 50%. But unfortunately, at the enterprise level, it will be more informative if the analysis is carried out on the basis of financial statements, rather than statistical data.

Responsibility to buyers and customers as one of the external vectors of management of social responsibility can be characterized only by the price index of industrial producers. During the study period, it really decreases dramatically from 125.4 in 2015. and 135.7 in 2016 to 92.6 in 2019 But this rather indicates an increase in the level of competition in the domestic market and a decrease in the purchasing power of buyers, rather than an increase in the level of social responsibility of enterprises.

The release of quality products is evidence of social responsibility to customers and customers. The cost of innovation of industrial enterprises at their own expense in 2015 amounted to 13427.0 million UAH, in 2017 there was not a significant decrease to 10742.0

million UAH. In 2019, these expenses amounted to UAH 12474.9 million.

To support of socially responsible enterprises, it is necessary to form a data system for the targeted use of funds. But due to the lack of non-financial reporting, such information is not available to the management bodies. The study was conducted on the basis of a survey of regional state administrations resulting in the following conclusions.

1. According to the survey, 64% of projects of social direction of enterprises relate to the external vector "Responsibility to the community," 21% are an example of responsibility for the preservation of the environment and resources, for 15% they cannot determine any separate direction and believe that these enterprises meet all areas of social responsibility.

2. In Ukraine, management does not see the feasibility and benefits of introducing social responsibility management in the enterprise. The state of this phenomenon is difficult to identify and assess at the state level due to the lack of reports, both at the enterprise level and at the level of state structures. Although such advantages are obvious, as evidenced by the matrix compiled by Sustain Ability based on an analysis of the activities of companies in Central and Eastern Europe. The matrix helps to identify the key elements of the feasibility of socially responsible business. It combines two groups of factors: business success, factors related to sustainable development. Where the factors in the directions converge, it is possible to determine the condition for the feasibility of the social responsibility [2].

Conducting a survey among the management of firms, it was found that the vast majority believe that the implementation of projects aimed at community development has an impact on reducing costs or increasing the productivity of the enterprise. Responsibility for the preservation of the environment and resources will not contribute to the diversification of markets, as well as the completeness and timeliness of payment of taxes and payments. Responsibility to buyers and customers will not reduce the company's costs, and activities aimed at responsible relations with contractors and partners will not contribute to revenue growth.

Most respondents do not consider it expedient to conduct responsible business before counterparties in order to gain access to capital or develop intellectual capital. Although, this is a false opinion, since partners can become investors in business, and the responsibility shown to partners can encourage professionals from other enterprises to change jobs in their favor. Experts believe that responsibility to state fiscal authorities and the state does not contribute to improving the image of the enterprise, but it is rather a national mentality, and not the real impact of this vector on the success factor.

Experts almost unanimously approve the impact of responsibility to the community on the possibility of diversifying sales markets and improving the conditions for access to capital. In addition, this vector at the level of responsibility to customers and customers have a decisive impact on the image of the enterprise. Responsibility for preserving the environment and resources will greatly contribute to reducing costs and in-

creasing productivity. Well, responsibility to state fiscal authorities and the state radically reduces costs, and responsibility to buyers and customers should stimulate an increase in revenues. Such a vector as responsibility to suppliers and partners does not have a decisive influence on any of the success factors. But this attitude, in our opinion, is literal and not strategic. According to the expert survey, only 20% believe that certain vectors of social responsibility management are decisive for the success of the enterprise.

If we compare the results with the results of a survey of European enterprises according to the methodology of Sustain Ability, then 38% of experts are inclined to believe that certain areas of social responsibility have a decisive influence on certain factors of business success. On the one hand, this is 18% more, and on the other hand, given that the understanding of the appropriateness of social responsibility by enterprises within the national economy has arisen quite recently, the results obtained can be considered satisfactory.

According to the expert assessment, the most significant results of the implementation of social responsibility measures for the management of domestic enterprises are such success factors as: growth of enterprise productivity; cost reduction; the possibility of diversification of sales markets. Significant can also be considered - income growth and the formation of a positive image of the enterprise. To determine priorities more effectively, it would be worthwhile to determine the importance of success factors for enterprises in the context of their size, that is, large, small, medium. This would allow us to prioritize the results of the implementation of social responsibility management measures depending on the capabilities of the enterprise.

Conclusion The necessity of forming a methodology for assessing the management of social responsibility for the needs of enterprise management by internal and external vectors has been substantiated. Evaluation of social responsibility vectors should be carried out according to the volume of social investments by their quality and efficiency. To form and implement such a methodology, the management of the enterprise must take the following measures: to develop a regulation on the social policy of the company; to form a system of criteria for the information base for making managerial decisions of a social direction; record and monitor the results of the implementation of social programs and the level of satisfaction of internal and external stakeholders with the results of their implementation; develop a form of non-financial report to identify trends in changes and the state of social responsibility of the enterprise.

The aim of developing or adjusting their own methodology is to eliminate errors and gaps by ensuring adequate systematization of information for management needs. This approach will not only provide an opportunity to assess the state of social responsibility, but also indicate ways to improve and further develop both the issue under study and the enterprise as a whole.

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